

ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY INDICATORS AND PERFORMANCE THRESHOLDS FOR RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS: A SCOPING REVIEW

J. C. KWIO-TAMALE¹, S.H.P. CHIKAFALIMANI², S. MOYO³ and N. KIBWAMI⁴

^{1,2}Department of Construction Management & Quantity Surveying, Durban University of Technology, South Africa.

³Research, Innovation and Postgraduate Studies, Stellenbosch University, South Africa.

⁴Department of Construction Economics & Management, Makerere University, Kampala, Uganda.

E-Mail: ¹tamalekwiojc@gmail.com, ¹22492830@dut4life.ac.za, ²samuelc@dut.ac.za, ³smoyo@sun.ac.za,

⁴nathan.kibwami@mak.ac.ug

ORCID: ¹<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4086-4570>, ²<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3555-2206>,

³<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5613-7290>, ⁴<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3639-3382>

Abstract

Construction depletes natural resources resulting in environmental degradation. This review aims to identify environmental sustainability indicators and performance thresholds in residential buildings. Using population-concept-context framework, 67 eligible literature from Scopus and Google Scholar databases and grey literature from 2020-2025 identified environmental sustainability domains as (1) land efficiency, (2) water efficiency, (3) energy efficiency, (4) material efficiency and (5) internal environmental quality with subdomains of (5.1) thermal comfort, (5.2) acoustic comfort, (5.3) visual comfort and (5.4) internal air quality. Environmental sustainability indicators and thresholds include ecological footprint $\leq 75\%$ and diameter at breast height representing biomass of $\geq 0.258 \text{ cm}^2$ for land efficiency; water saving rates of $\geq 80\%$ and water exploitation rates at $\leq 20\%$; renewable energy of $\geq 60\%$ and energy use intensity limited at $60 \text{ kWh/m}^2/\text{year}$. Embodied and operational carbon intensities of $\leq 11 \text{ kgCO}_2\text{eq/m}^2/\text{year}$ minimizes climate change. Visual comfort requires 100-300 lux for daylight factors of 1-5%, acoustic comfort occurs at sound pressure levels of 43-63 dB and cross-ventilation at window-to-wall ratios of 20-40% and window-to-floor-area ratios $\geq 8\%$ ensures air change hourly rates of $0.3\text{-}1.0 \text{ H}^{-1}$ for internal air quality. The study supports policies, practice and research in sustainable design of new and retrofitting of existing buildings in managing the built environment better.

Keywords: Environmental Sustainability, Indicators, Performance Thresholds, Residential Buildings.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

In 1972, the Club of Rome published “*The Limits To Growth*” in which they warned on depletion of environmental resources in 100 years (Collombert et al., 2024; Greer et al., 2020; Grunkemeyer & Moss, 2020, p. 11). Subsequently, Sicignano et al. (2019, p. 1) projected that 75% of the remaining environmental resources would be exhausted by 2050 under the present wasteful economic system (de Sa & Korinek, 2021, p. 6). These warnings remain valid to date (Kroeck, 2023, p. 2) because over-exploitation of environmental resources exceeds its self-regeneration rate (Skånberg & Wijkman, 2017, pp. 5, 12). Consequently, the massive material extraction has tripled in the last 50 years resulting in crossing of five planetary boundaries (Cundiff et al., 2023, p. 2). This unlimited economic growth is at the expense of environmental

sustainability (Kroeck, 2023, p. 2) because of the environmentally over-consumptive construction industry (Simwero et al., 2024, p. 248) through environmental depletion and degradation. Sustainable consumption is a key concept in the 1987 United Nations World Commission on Environment and Development report (Holden et al., 2017, p. 176). Consequently, governments pursue environmental protection and green policies to ensure sustainable construction (Goh et al., 2020, p. 7). However, there is no framework for environmental sustainability performance thresholds and protocols in the built environment

1.2 Aim and Objectives of the Paper

The unsustainable consumption of finite environmental resources remains the main root cause of the three ecological crises of climate change, biodiversity loss and pollution worldwide (Damiyano et al., 2023, p. 24). This situation calls for urgent establishment and observance of consumption limits for environmental resources. However, the lack of some environmental sustainability performance thresholds and weak enforcement of existing ones in construction frustrates efforts to sustainable development in the built environment. Therefore, the aim of this paper is to contribute to environmental sustainability in residential building construction. To achieve this aim, the following objectives are set to: (1) identify environmental sustainability domains, (2) identify indicators and their sustainability performance thresholds for environmental sustainability domains in construction and (3) identify knowledge gaps in environmental sustainability performance thresholds.

1.3 Contribution of the Paper

Knowledge on environmental sustainability domains, indicators and performance thresholds in the built environment promotes sustainable management of environmental resources. This is achievable by using environmental limits in: (1) sustainable design of new and (2) retrofitting of existing buildings. This approach avoids low utilization and early retirement of built infrastructure as stranded capital stock before recouping the initial and maintenance capital investments in them. This benefits built environment professionals, academics and real estate practitioners in the design, construction and facility maintenance of built environment.

1.4 Organization of the Paper

Section 1 of this paper introduces environmental sustainability in residential buildings, Section 2 presents literature review on environmental sustainability domains, indicators and performance thresholds for sustainable residential buildings. Section 3 presents methodology for the study. Section 4 presents and discusses findings of environmental sustainability indicators and performance thresholds for sustainable residential buildings. Section 5 concludes the paper with recommendations and identified future research.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Environmental Sustainability Domains and Indicators

According to (Greer et al., 2020, pp. 4, 14), sustainability frameworks include: (1) energy, (2) health, (3) water and wastewater, (4) land, (5) materials and (6) multidimensional. The first

five of these are environmental sustainability domains for green construction (Abukhalaf, 2021, p. 1; Anzagira et al., 2021, p. 17).

Sustainability indicators have thresholds to assess environmental sustainability (Carlucci et al., 2015, p. 10). By defining ‘*safe and just operating space*’ as the distance of “*safe zone*’ from planetary boundaries (Global Footprint Network Research Team, 2020, p. 18), sustainability indicators: (1) compare and (2) identify weak points and opportunities for improving sustainability of facilities and infrastructure and (3) measure progress towards sustainable development goals (Global Footprint Network Research Team, 2020, p. 2).

2.1.1 Land Efficiency

Ecological footprint is the physical human demand for natural resources from the earth’s biocapacity (biologically productive space of land and water) that provides ecological services (Global Footprint Network Research Team, 2020, pp. 3, 9-10, 17). Ecological footprint assesses lifecycle consumption at all scales (Global Footprint Network Research Team, 2020, p. 11) as indicator of land efficiency in sustainable construction (Bulti & Assefa, 2019, p. 2). Linear relationships exist between ecological footprint and family size, floor area and plot area (Bulti & Assefa, 2019, p. 1). Therefore, plot ratio that relates built area to plot area measures ecological footprint (Pakistani Ministry of Energy, 2023, p. 41). Sustainable urban authorities specify plot ratios to ensure landscape vegetation for land efficiency (International Energy Agency, 2021a, p. 43). This is because natural green areas sequester (store) carbon dioxide (Bulti & Assefa, 2019, p. 4) and reduce solar heat radiation (Pakistani Ministry of Energy, 2023, p. 56) to promote thermal comfort.

2.1.2 Water Efficiency

Water consumption is the difference between water abstraction and water returned to the environment before or after use and water efficiency index (WEI) measures water consumption as percentage of renewable freshwater resources (European Environment Agency, 2025). WEI values over 20% signifies water stress and water scarcity (European Environment Agency, 2025). To align with United Nations Sustainable Development Goal Indicator 6.4 for sustainable management of water resources, WEI values above 40% signify severity of water stress and unsustainable freshwater use (European Environment Agency, 2025). This means that maximum threshold for water efficiency is 20%. Another metric close to WEI is the water conservation index (also known as water saving rate) which is the ratio of actual water used in buildings to the average estimated water consumption (Sivasankar et al., 2016, p. 832).

2.1.3 Energy Efficiency

Energy is a scarce resource for economic development and public welfare (Yang et al., 2024, p. 1959). Energy efficient buildings reduce emissions from 55-70% (Bera et al., 2025, p. 4) through solarization and responsible behaviours (United Nations Environment Programme, 2022, p. 44). Energy use intensity is a useful indicator for residential energy efficiency (Osterberg, 2024, pp. 3, 14). The 2015 Paris Agreement advocates for Stated Policies Scenarios (STEPS) (International Energy Agency, 2021a, pp. 30-31) like Nationally Determined

Contributions (NDCs) as high-level country policy commitments and initiatives to reduce carbon emissions and climate change (International Energy Agency, 2021a, pp. 30-31; United Nations Environment Programme, 2022, p. 18). Accordingly, energy consumption is a common sustainability assessment indicator (Greer et al., 2020, p. 14). Figure 1 shows that by 2018, energy efficiencies of South Africa and Tunisia were above 67%, those of Kenya, Cameroon, Ghana, Egypt, Algeria and Morocco were 33-67% and majority of Africa trailed between 0-33% (World Bank, 2018, p. 81).

Source: World Bank RISE 2018

Figure 1: 2017 Global outlook of energy efficiency (%)

Source: (World Bank, 2018, p. 82)

Buildings consume 33-35% of global energy consumption and release 25-40% carbon emissions (Bera et al., 2025, p. 15; Council of Europe Development Bank, 2024, p. 7; United Nations Environment Programme, 2022, pp. 15, 35). Residential buildings in particular consume up to 66% of energy in buildings (International Energy Agency, 2021a; Tanzania Ministry of Energy, 2024, p. 2). Therefore, the built environment provides the largest opportunity for decarbonization (International Renewable Energy Agency, 2018, p. 33). Energy performance indicators measure energy consumption per unit output like Energy Use Intensity (EUI) (United Nations Environment Programme, 2022, p. 46). Renewable energy is a typical sustainability indicator (Collombert et al., 2024, p. 38; Greer et al., 2020, p. 7) and should be upscaled by 600% for the world to comply with Paris Agreement for climate change control (International Renewable Energy Agency, 2018, p. 8). This is achievable by increasing renewable energy from 15-67% in total primary energy supply between 2015-2050 (International Renewable Energy Agency, 2018, p. 9) to comply with German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development (2015, p. 44) target of 60% renewable energy to achieve 54% energy efficiency in buildings.

2.1.4 Material Efficiency

Embodied energy is the total energy and related carbon emissions from extraction, processing, manufacturing, transportation, assembly, disassembly and disposal of construction materials after useful life (International Energy Agency, 2021a, p. 93). The cumulative carbon emission of buildings is projected to be 30 GtCO₂e/yr between 2019-2070 (International Energy Agency, 2021a, p. 55). Life expectancy of buildings range between 30-150 years and over 50% of existing buildings may last up to 2050 (International Energy Agency, 2021a, p. 60). This trend is unsustainable because it threatens with 50% probability (International Energy Agency, 2021a, p. 39) to exhaust the remaining carbon budget to control global warming below the recommended 2°C target (International Energy Agency, 2021a, p. 55). Cement and steel that are hard to decarbonize dominate construction. Therefore, enhancing material efficiency requires recycling and reuse of materials and a paradigm shift to biobased materials (International Energy Agency, 2021a, p. 93).

Material reuse and recycling reduces carbon emissions (Arya et al., 2025, p. 2) and therefore requires behavioural change to reduce energy demand by 10-15% to realise net zero energy buildings by 2050 (International Energy Agency, 2021a, p. 68). Material efficiency is required urgently to achieve net zero carbon goal because: (1) current carbon reducing technologies are in initial phases of demonstration and deployment and (2) the traditional high embodied energy manufacturing investments like cement plants have long lifespans from 25-40 years (International Energy Agency, 2021a, p. 232; 2021b, p. 39) . Therefore, the long payback periods for manufacturing investments for high carbon materials disincentivise premature decommissioning of such assets.

2.1.5 Internal Environmental Quality

Internal Environmental Quality (IEQ) comprises the four subdomains of: (1) visual comfort, (2) thermal comfort, (3) acoustic comfort and (4) internal air quality (IAQ) (Muriel et al., 2021, p. 1; Tewari & Singh, 2021, p. 1).

2.1.5.1 Visual Comfort

Passive design uses natural daylight in buildings to save electric light energy and avoid energy-intensive mechanical ventilation (Pakistani Ministry of Energy, 2023, p. 50). According to the Pakistani Ministry of Energy (2023, p. 49), daylight factor that expresses distribution and penetration of indoor light intensity is expressed as:

$$DF = (E_{internal} / E_{external}) \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

Where:

DF = Daylight factor (%)

$E_{internal}$ = horizontal illumination at indoor reference point (lux)

$E_{external}$ = horizontal illumination at unobstructed outdoor point in clear sky condition (lux)

To ensure acceptable (1) lighting, (2) glare and (3) solar heat gain hence thermal comfort,

daylight factor should range 1.0-3.5% (Pakistani Ministry of Energy, 2023, pp. 49-50) with average daylight factors, $A_vDF > 2\%$ (living rooms) and $A_vDF > 1.5\%$ (bedrooms) (Erba et al., 2021, p. 39).

2.1.5.2 Thermal Comfort

The American Society of Heating, Refrigeration and Air-conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE) Standard 55 indoor thermal comfort range is 18-32°C (Tewari & Singh, 2021, p. 12). This departs from the single-point thermal comfort temperature of 25.6°C for northern temperate zones posited by Professor Fanger in 1967-1970s (Alwetaishi, 2016, p. 930).

2.1.5.3 Acoustic Comfort

Sound Pressure Level (SPL) is an indicator of acoustic comfort (Hamida et al., 2023, pp. 1, 8).

2.1.5.4 Internal Air Quality

Internal air quality (IAQ) that measures air pollution on indoor occupants' health is important because people spend 90% of time indoors (Dodd et al., 2021, p. 1; Katunský et al., 2021, p. 1), Passive ventilation through outdoor and indoor air exchange enhances IAQ (Miguel et al., 2022, p. 85; Savanti et al., 2022, p. 219).

3. METHODS AND MATERIALS

Unlike systematic reviews that identify and synthesize available literature on focused research questions, scoping reviews explore primary inquiries to map the breadth of available and evolving literature on topics to identify concepts and knowledge gaps (Grønstad, 2025, p. 5; Khalil et al., 2025, pp. 1-2). The PCC (population-concept-context) framework suits scoping reviews better than other research question frameworks (Well Cornell Medicine Library, 2025). Structured on the Joanna Briggs Institute approach, the PCC elements for this study are residential buildings (*population*), environmental sustainability (*concept*) and the built environment (*context*). Eligibility inclusion criteria are full-text English publications during 2020-2025 and exclusion criteria are abstracts-only and non-English publications from Scopus and Google Scholar databases resulting in 67 eligible sources for review. Search strings of 'environmental sustainability AND environmental sustainability domains AND sustainable construction AND environmental sustainability thresholds' were implemented in EndNote.

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents and discusses: (1) environmental sustainability domains and (2) environmental sustainability performance thresholds for sustainable residential building construction.

4.1 Environmental Sustainability Domains

The five dominant environmental sustainability domains in residential built environment are land efficiency, water efficiency, energy efficiency, material efficiency and internal environmental quality.

4.2 Environmental Sustainability Performance Thresholds

The performance thresholds for sustainable residential building construction are as follows:

4.2.1 Performance Thresholds for Land Efficiency Indicators

Maximum plot areas <75% (Pakistani Ministry of Energy, 2023, p. 41) at ground area implies that floor area can be increased by vertical densification to have high floor area ratios (FARs). This optimizes land through compact development and less urban sprawl. A high FAR maximizes space and minimizes direct ecological footprint. Two trees each of minimum 60 cm diameter at breast height (DBH) and each with minimum crown spread of 9 metres per 465 m² plot promotes land efficiency (U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, 2008, pp. 12-13). This means that the minimum DBH = 2 x 60 cm / 465 m² ≈ 0.258 cm/m².

4.2.2 Performance Thresholds for Water Efficiency Indicators

The maximum water exploitation rate is 20% for sustainable use of freshwater. Therefore, water efficiency can be adjudged as 100% for water exploitation rates of ≤20%. This corresponds to the recommended water conservation ratio of ≥80% (Sivasankar et al., 2016, p. 834).

4.2.3 Performance Thresholds for Energy Efficiency Indicators

Table 1 shows thresholds for energy use intensity as energy efficiency indicator.

Table 1: Energy use intensity thresholds for sustainable construction in residential buildings

S. No.	Study Reference Source	Energy efficiency Indicator	Environmental Sustainability Thresholds	
			Minimum	Maximum
1	Energy Star Portfolio Manager (2025)	EUI in the USA		188 kWh/m ² /yr
2	Energy Star Portfolio Manager (2025)	EUI in Canada		228-336 kWh/m ² /yr
3	Saygin et al. (2019, p. 25)	EUI in The European Union		50-90 kwh/m ² .year.
4	Saygin et al. (2019, p. 25)	EUI in Estonia		200-400 kWh/m ² /year
5	Collombert et al. (2024, p. 47)	EUI in office buildings in The Netherlands		225 kWh/m ² /year
6	Irish Department of Housing Local Government and Heritage (2023, pp. 16-17)	EUI in Irish buildings		125 kWh/m ² /yr
7	Sustainable and Renewable Energy Development Authority (2023, p. 10)	Baseline energy consumption in Dhaka-Bangladesh		277 kWh/m ² per year
8	Centre for Energy Efficiency (2013, pp. 13, 101)	EUI in Uzbekistan	0-50 kWh/m ² /year for passive design (average 15 kWh/m ² per year)	80-160 kWh/m ² / year
9	International Green Council (2025)	EUI in residential buildings		68 kWh/m ² / year
10	MacGregor et al. (2018, p. 24)	EUI in New Zealand residential buildings		60 kWh/m ² / year

Table 1 shows that EUI in USA, Canada, Europe, Asia and New Zealand varies between 50-400 kWh/m²/year. The Passive House Institute of New Zealand, based on the Passive House Standard *Passivhaus* building approach from Germany's *Passivhaus-Institut* limits domestic operational EUI to 60 kWh/m²/yr (MacGregor et al., 2018, p. 24). This is close to the prescriptive primary renewable energy for residential buildings of 68 kWh/m²/yr specified in Section 7.4.1.1 of the 2021 International Green Construction Code (International Green Council, 2025). The EUIs of 200-400 kWh/m²/year are considered wasteful in Estonia (Saygin et al., 2019, p. 25). This encourages decarbonization of buildings that requires 45-50% EUI reduction between 2030-2050 (Bera et al., 2025, pp. 2-3). The target of complete decarbonization in the built environment by 2050 (Aldersgate Group, 2017, p. 4) suggests deep retrofitting of existing buildings.

4.2.4 Performance Thresholds for Visual Comfort Indicators

Table 2 shows the recommended indoor illuminance thresholds in residential buildings.

Table 2: Visual comfort indicator threshold for sustainable construction in residential buildings

S. No.	Study Reference Source	Internal Environmental Quality Subdomain: Daylight (Visual) Comfort Indicator	Environmental Sustainability Thresholds	
			Minimum	Maximum
1	Sustainable and Renewable Energy Development Authority (2023, p. 31)	Illuminance in Bangladesh (From natural daylight at work plane height (1m) in regularly occupied area under clear sky.)	150 Lux	
2	SOLID Green Consulting (2023, pp. 28-29)	Illuminance in Nigeria	300 lux (Living rooms and kitchen), 200 lux (bedrooms), 150 lux (toilets, bathrooms and corridors)	
3	Bureau of Energy Efficiency (2017, p. 17)	Illuminance in India (taken at a work plane height of 0.8 m above finished floor for at least 90% of the potential daylight time in a year)	100 lux	2,000 lux
4	Pakistani Ministry of Energy (2023, p. 36)	Illuminance in Pakistan	300 lux Spatial Daylight Autonomy (SDA) of 50% /year i.e. SDA300/50%	1,000 lux Annual Sunlight Exposure (ASE) at 250 hours/year i.e. ASE1000/250
5	Sustainable and Renewable Energy Development Authority (2023, p. 31)	Illuminance in Bangladesh		5,000 lux to avoid glare
6	Carlucci et al. (2015, p. 13)	Generalized	300-500 lux	
7	Zhong et al. (2021, p. 3)	Generalized	500 lux	1,000 lux
8	Erba et al. (2021, p. 40)	Africa and Europe	150 lux	2,000 lux

Bioclimatic design with recommended indoor daylight illuminance 100-300 lux against external daylight illuminance up to 5,000 lux in Table 2 results in daylight factors that exceed 4% marginally. This is close to the recommended design daylight factor range of 1.0-3.5% in equation 1. This means that passive design with the above range of indoor daylight illuminance achieves visual comfort. Illuminance of 300-500 lux is considered acceptable for daylight quantity (Carlucci et al., 2015, p. 13). This complies with International Standard Organization ISO 8995:2000 standard of illuminance range of 150-2,000 lux (Erba et al., 2021, p. 40).

4.2.5 Performance Thresholds for Acoustic Comfort Indicators

The World Bank recommended SPL in residential buildings is 35-50 dB (Rockwool, 2023, p. 9). These sound pressures are within the limit of 70 dB below which there is no hearing impairment for prolonged lifetime noise exposure for people of all ages (Camusso, 2010, p. 311). Speech transmission index (STI) ranges from 0.00 (bad) to 1.00 (excellent) (Hamida et al., 2023, p. 8; Taghipour et al., 2020, p. 8).

4.2.6 Performance Thresholds for Thermal Comfort Indicators

The ISO Standard 7730 for summer thermal comfort zone is 23°C-26°C (Miguel et al., 2022, p. 86; Savanti et al., 2022, p. 220) accommodates majority of studies whose optimal thermal comfort zones ranges from 23-28°C.

However, this departs from Professor Fanger's single-point 25.6°C thermal comfort threshold for temperate climate. However, the mid-point 25.5°C of trapezoidal temperature distribution range of 23-28°C is close to the single-point 25.6°C thermal comfort threshold with a negligibly marginal difference of 0.1°C. Therefore, 23-28°C optimal thermal comfort zone is more realistic than the single-point 25.6°C.

4.2.7 Performance Thresholds for Internal Air Quality Indicators

The two manifest indicators for passive design for internal air quality in residential buildings are areal ratios of: (1) window to wall ratio (WWR) and (2) window to floor ratio (WFR). The maximum WWR ranges 20-40% with 40% as majority. The minimum WFR is $\geq 8\%$ (International Code Council Incorporation, 2021). This provides ASHRAE Standard 62.1 minimum air change hourly rate of 0.35/hour to cross-ventilate residential buildings for acceptable internal air quality (Savanti et al., 2022, p. 219).

4.2.8 Importance Weights of Environmental Sustainability Indicators in Buildings

Feature importance weights are correlations that express the unique contributions of variables in multi-criterial indices (Schumacker & Lomax, 2004, p. 137). Table 3 summarizes the importance weights for the subdomains of internal environmental quality in buildings.

Table 3 displays both equal weight and unequal weight importance weights for environmental sustainability domains. It is most unlikely that these domains have equal weights because of their likely different contributions in multi-criterial indices. Besides, some importance weights were subjective as in (Piasecki et al., 2020, p. 9).

Table 3: Importance weights of environmental internal quality subdomains in buildings

No.	Studies	Thermal Comfort	Acoustic Comfort	Visual Comfort	Internal Air Quality	Statistical Analysis
1	Astolfi and Pellerrey (2008)	33%	26%	20%	21%	PCA
2	Lee et al. (2012, pp. 10-15)	22%	39%	21%	18%	Subjective
3	Catalina and Iordache (2012)	25%	25%	25%	25%	MNLR
4	Thasildoost and Zomorodian (2018, p. 18)	34%	26%	31%	9%	PCA
5	Piasecki et al. (2020, p. 9)	25%	25%	25%	25%	MADM
6	Leccese et al. (2021, p. 11)	43%	16%	24%	17%	AHP
7	Erba et al. (2021, p. 58)	30%	18%	16%	18%	MVLR
8	Erba et al. (2021, p. 58)	21%	20%	16%	29%	MVLgR
9	Erba et al. (2021, p. 58)	32%	22%	17%	12%	RWF

Legend: PCA = Principal Component Analysis, MNLR= Multivariate Non-Linear Regression, MADM=Multi Attribute Decision Making Method, AHP= Analytic Hierarchical Process, MVLR= Multivariate Linear Regression, MVLgR= Multivariate Logistic Regression, RWF=Relative weight factor

Therefore, the equal arithmetic average additive importance weights of Catalina and Iordache (2012), Lee et al. (2012, p. 15), Piasecki et al. (2020, p. 9) and Leccese et al. (2021, p. 14) may not be realistic hence applicable. Besides, the weights of environmental sustainability indicators that contribute individually and cumulatively to the environmental domains and subdomains need to be determined.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER RESEARCH

The following **key environmental sustainability indicators for sustainable residential buildings** are: (1) ecological footprint and (2) landscape vegetation for land efficiency; (3) renewable energy ratio in total energy mix and (4) energy use intensity for energy efficiency; (5) age of infrastructure, (6) embodied energy, (7) material reuse and recycling and (8) biogenic materials for material efficiency. The applicable **environmental performance thresholds for the above environmental sustainability indicators** include: (1) The ratio of renewable energy in total energy mix is the most direct measure of energy efficiency indicator for transition to carbon zero future because Energy Use Intensity includes non-renewable carbon-emissive energy. (2) Water Conservation Index (Water Saving Rate) is a more direct measure and better indicator than Water Exploitation Index for water efficiency in residential buildings because some abstracted water may not be used and returns to underground reservoir. (3) The highest safe 70 dB sound intensity that is applicable to majority people of all ages for prolonged exposure throughout life offers the maximum tolerance limit for modelling internal environmental quality for sustainable residential buildings. (5) Embodied energy of building materials is a pathway for managing energy efficiency in buildings. Therefore, energy efficiency that relates bidirectionally to material efficiency in buildings can be modelled by material efficiency. (6) The optimal temperature range of 23-28°C for thermal comfort in residential buildings is more realistic than single-point 25.6°C thermal comfort threshold because thermal comfort zone accommodates physiological conditions for people compared to single-point temperature.

The following actions are recommended: (1) Energy efficiency should be modelled by classifying energy use intensities up to 60 kWh/m²/year as energy efficient beyond which energy efficiency declines to zero at and beyond 200 kWh/m²/year because of operational wastage. (2) Energy use intensities significantly below the average passive design threshold of 60 kWh/m²/year should be counter-checked by ratio of renewable energy in total energy mix indicator because EUI indicators may have carbon-emissive non-renewable energies. (3) Water Conservation Index (Water Saving Rate) which is a more direct indicator of water consumption than water exploitation index should be preferred in modelling water efficiency for sustainable residential buildings to minimize modelling error. (4) To comply with the eco-efficiency concept of combining energy efficiency and material efficiency in life cycle engineering, model energy efficiency with material efficiency as predictor. (5) Thermo-neutral thermal comfort zone for internal environmental quality in residential buildings should be modelled in relation to thermal comfort 23-28°C temperature range. Based on the identified **knowledge gaps of:** (1) no statistically-determined feature importance weights of environmental sustainability indicators for policy decision-making and (2) no models for environmental sustainability in residential buildings, **further research** is needed to: (1) determine importance weights of environmental sustainability indicators empirically instead of assuming equal arithmetic average weights in additive models and (2) model environmental sustainability in residential buildings for sustainable construction.

Conflict of Interest

We do not have conflict of interest in this paper.

References

- 1) Abukhalaf, A. H. I. (2021). Legal complications in U.S green construction. *Academia Letters*. <https://doi.org/10.20935/al2576>
- 2) Aldersgate Group. (2017). *Energy efficiency in the UK's buildings: key priorities for the new government*. A. Group.
- 3) Alwetaishi, M. S. (2016). Impact of building function on thermal comfort: a review paper. *American Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences*, 94(4), 928-945. <https://doi.org/https://doi: 10.3844/ajeassp.2016.928.945>
- 4) Anzagira, L. F., Duah, D. Y., & Badu, E. (2021). Awareness and application of green building concepts by construction industry stakeholders of sub-Saharan African countries. *Journal of Sustainable Development Studies*, 14(2).
- 5) Arya, Y., Sagar, & Poonam, S. (2025). Energy efficient green building design utilizing renewable energy and low-carbon development technologies. *Science and Technology for Energy Transition* 80 25. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2516/stet/2025004>
- 6) Astolfi, A., & Pellerrey, F. (2008). Subjective and objective assessment of acoustical and overall environmental quality in secondary school classrooms. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 123(1), 163-173. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1121/1.2816563>
- 7) Bera, M., Das, S., Garai, S., Dutta, S., Roy Choudhury, M., Tripathi, S., & Chatterjee, G. (2025). Advancing energy efficiency: innovative technologies and strategic measures for achieving net zero emissions. *Carbon Footprints*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.20517/cf.2024.48>

- 8) Bulti, D. T., & Assefa, T. (2019). Analyzing ecological footprint of residential building construction in Adama City, Ethiopia. *Environmental Systems Research*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40068-019-0130-8>
- 9) Bureau of Energy Efficiency. (2017). *Energy conservation building code*. Bureau of Energy Efficiency.
- 10) Camusso, C. (2010). Transport, environment and sustainability. In *Indicators of environmental sustainability in transport: An interdisciplinary approach to methods*. Institut national de recherche sur les transports et leur sécurité-INRETS.
- 11) Carlucci, S., Causone, F., De Rosa, F., & Pagliano, L. (2015). A review of indices for assessing visual comfort with a view to their use in optimization processes to support building integrated design. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*. <http://authors.elsevier.com/a/1QoR34s9HvhKig>
- 12) Catalina, T., & Iordache, V. (2012). Indoor environmental quality assessment on schools in the design stage. *Building and Environment* 49(1), 129-140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2011.09.014>
- 13) Centre for Energy Efficiency. (2013). *Energy efficiency in buildings: Untapped reserves for Uzbekistan sustainable development*.
- 14) Collombert, R., Peillon, R. H., & Joyce, A. (2024). *Energy performance of buildings directive (EPBD) 2024: Implementation guide*. efficientbuildings.eu
- 15) Council of Europe Development Bank. (2024). *Improving energy efficiency in housing: Why evaluation matters*. Council of Europe Development Bank (CEB). <https://coebank.org/en/news-and-publications/ceb-publications/CEB-Improving-energy-efficiency-in-housing/>
- 16) Cundiff, B., Trottier-Chi, C., Smith, R., Beck, M., & Chris Bataille, C. (2023). *How circularity can contribute to emissions reductions in Canada*.
- 17) Damiyano, D., Mago, S., & Dorasamy, N. (2023). A systematic review of sustainable consumption and production in africa. *Africagrowth Agenda*, 20(4), 24-30.
- 18) de Sa, P., & Korinek, J. (2021). *Resource efficiency, the circular economy, sustainable materials management and trade in metals and minerals: OECD trade policy paper No. 245*. OECD Publishing.
- 19) Dodd, N., Donatello, S., & Cordella, M. (2021). *Level(s) indicator 5.2: Increased risk of extreme weather events user manual: introductory briefing, instructions and guidance (Publication version 1.1)*. European Commission Joint Research Centre. <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc>
- 20) Energy Star Portfolio Manager. (2025). Energy benchmarking. <https://natural-resources.canada.ca/energy-efficiency/energy-star/energy-benchmarking-energy-starr-portfolio-managerr>
- 21) Erba, S., Barbieri, A., & Pagliano, L. (2021). *Africa-Europe bioclimatic buildings for the 21st century: report on comfort indicators and scenarios*. E. Commission.
- 22) European Environment Agency. (2025, 23 March 2024). Water scarcity conditions in Europe. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/indicators/use-of-freshwater-resources-in-europe-1>
- 23) German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development. (2015). *Energy efficiency strategy for buildings: Methods for achieving a virtually climate-neutral building stock*. German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development (BMWi). www.bmwi.de
- 24) Global Footprint Network Research Team. (2020). *Ecological footprint accounting: Limitations and criticism*
- 25) Goh, C. S., Chong, H.-Y., Jack, L., & Mohd Faris, A. F. (2020). Revisiting triple bottom line within the context of sustainable construction: A systematic review. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 252. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.119884>

- 26) Greer, F., Rakas, J., & Horvath, A. (2020). Airports and environmental sustainability: a comprehensive review. *Environmental Research Letters*, 15(10). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/abb42a>
- 27) Grønstad, A. (2025). Scoping reviews vis-à-vis systematic reviews and integrative reviews in management research: guidelines for good practice. *Review of Managerial Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11846-025-00901-1>
- 28) Grunkemeyer, W., & Moss, M. (2020). *Key concepts in sustainable development*. <https://researchrepository.wvu.edu/rri-web-book>
- 29) Hamida, A., Zhang, D., Ortiz, M. A., & Bluysen, P. M. (2023). Indicators and methods for assessing acoustical preferences and needs of students in educational buildings: A review. *Applied Acoustics*, 202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apacoust.2022.109187>
- 30) Holden, E., Linnerud, K., & Banister, D. (2017). The imperatives of sustainable development. *Sustainable Development*, 25(3), 213–226. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.1647>
- 31) International Code Council Incorporation. (2021). 2021 International Building Code. <https://www.iccsafe.org/adoptions>
- 32) International Energy Agency. (2021a). *Net Zero by 2050: A roadmap for the global energy sector*. www.iea.org/corrections
- 33) International Energy Agency. (2021b). *Energy perspectives technology 2020*. International Energy Agency. www.iea.org/corrections
- 34) International Green Council. (2025). *International Green Council Code (IgCC) 2021*. National Institute of Building Sciences. <https://www.wbdg.org/resources/green-building-standards-and-certification-systems>
- 35) International Renewable Energy Agency. (2018). *Global energy transition: A roadmap to 2050*. P. a. F. C. K. Knowledge.
- 36) Irish Department of Housing Local Government and Heritage. (2023). *Improving energy efficiency in traditional buildings: Guidance for specifiers and installers*. www.gov.ie/housing
- 37) Katunský, D., Bullová, I., & Kapalo, P. (2021). Quantification of air change rate by selected methods in a typical apartment building. *Buildings* 2021., 11(174). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings11040174>
- 38) Khalil, H., Jia, R., Moraes, E. B., Munn, Z., Alexander, L., Peters, M. D. J., Asran, A., Godfrey, C. M., Tricco, A. C., Pollock, D., & Evans, C. (2025). Scoping reviews and their role in identifying research priorities. *J Clin Epidemiol*, 181, 111712. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2025.111712>
- 39) Kroeck, T. (2023). Mobilising towards environmental sustainability: Challenges and chances for churches in Germany. *Verbum et Ecclesia* 44(1), 2074-7705. <https://doi.org/10.4102/ve.v44i1.2701>
- 40) Leccese, F., Rocca, M., Salvadori, G., Belloni, E., & Buratti, C. (2021). Towards a holistic approach to indoor environmental quality assessment: Weighting schemes to combine effects of multiple environmental factors. *Energy and Buildings* 245(4). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2021.111056>
- 41) Lee, M. C., Mui, K. W., Wong, L. T., W Y, Lee, E. W. M., & Cheung, C. T. (2012). Student learning performance and indoor environmental quality (IEQ) in airconditioned university teaching rooms. *Building and Environment*, 49(238-244). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2011.10.001>
- 42) MacGregor, C., Dowdell, D., Jaques, R., Bint, L., & Berg, B. (2018). *The built environment and climate change: A review of research, challenges and the future BRANZ study report SR403*. BRANZ Ltd.

- 43) Miguel, C. A., Mora, D., Bruneau, D., & Sempey, A. (2022). A review of airflow rate estimation techniques for natural ventilation in buildings. *Redin*, 143, 83-100. <https://doi.org/https://www.doi.org/10.17533/udea.redin.20210849>
- 44) Muriel, D., Piderit, B. M., & Attia, S. (2021). Parameters and indicators used in indoor environmental quality (IEQ) studies: a review. *Journal of Physics Conference Series*, 2042 012132. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2042/1/012132>
- 45) Osterberg, A. (2024). *Advancing energy efficiency in residential buildings: Next steps for implementing the Thurston climate mitigation plan developed for the climate action steering committee*. Thurston Regional Planning Council.
- 46) Pakistani Ministry of Energy. (2023). *Energy conservation building code 2023*. National Energy Efficiency and Conservation Authority.
- 47) Piasecki, M., Radziszewska-Zielina, E., Czerski, P., Fedorczyk-Cisak, M., Zielina, M., Krzyściak, P., Kwaśniewska-Sip, P., & Grześkowiak, W. (2020). Implementation of the indoor environmental quality (IEQ) model for the assessment of a retrofitted historical masonry building. *Journal of Energies*, 13(22). <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13226051>
- 48) Rockwool. (2023). *Indoor acoustic comfort in buildings*. N. E. Centre.
- 49) Savanti, F., Setyowati, E., & Hardiman, G. (2022). The impact of ventilation on indoor air quality and air change rate. *Evergreen*, 9(1), 219-225. <https://doi.org/10.5109/4774237>
- 50) Saygin, D., Ercumen, Y., De Groote, M., & Bean, F. (2019). *Enhancing Turkey's policy framework for energy efficiency of buildings and recommendations for the way forward based on international experiences*. SHURA Energy Transition Center and Buildings Performance Institute Europe.
- 51) Schumacker, R. E., & Lomax, R. G. (2004). *A beginner's guide to structural equation modeling* (2nd ed.). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- 52) Sicignano, E., Di Ruocco, G., & Melella, R. (2019). Mitigation strategies for reduction of embodied energy and carbon in the construction systems of contemporary quality architecture. *Sustainability*, 11(14). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11143806>
- 53) Simwero, J., Ajwang, P., & Sanewu, F. (2024). Comparing between the awareness and adoption of sustainable construction practices in Kenya. *East African Journal of Engineering*, 7(1), 247-261. <https://doi.org/10.37284/eaje.7.1.2131>
- 54) Sivasankar, R., Sivasubramanian, C., Malarvannan, J., Jeganathan, M., & Balakumari, M. (2016). A study on water conservation aspects of green buildings. *Life Science Archives (LSA)*, 2(6), 832-836. <https://doi.org/10.21276/lisa.2016.2.6.8>
- 55) Skånberg, K., & Wijkman, A. (2017). *The circular economy and benefits for society jobs and climate clear Wwnners in an economy based on renewable energy and resource efficiency*. www.clubofrome.org
- 56) SOLID Green Consulting. (2023). *Development of the national building energy efficiency code (BEEC)*. W. a. H. H. S. Federal Ministry of Power.
- 57) Sustainable and Renewable Energy Development Authority. (2023). *Building energy efficiency and environment rating: Guidelines for new constructions and existing buildings*. SREDA.
- 58) Taghipour, A., Athari, S., Gisladdottir, A., Sievers, T., & Kurt Eggenschwiler, K. (2020). Room acoustical parameters as predictors of acoustic comfort in outdoor spaces of housing complexes. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11(344). <https://doi.org/doi:10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00344>

- 59) Tanzania Ministry of Energy. (2024). *National energy strategy 2024-2034*. Tanzania Ministry of Energy.
- 60) Tewari, P., & Singh, A. P. (2021). *Thermal comfort prescription for cooling dominated Indian residential buildings*. The Energy and Resources Institute.
- 61) Thasildoost, M., & Zomorodian, M. (2018). Indoor environment quality assessment in classrooms: An integrated approach. *Journal of Building Physics*, 42(3). <https://doi.org/10.1177/1744259118759687>
- 62) U.S. Environmental Protection Agency. (2008). *EPA's report on the environment*. U.S. Environmental Protection Agency.
- 63) United Nations Environment Programme. (2022). *2022 Global status report for buildings and construction: Towards a zero-emissions, efficient and resilient buildings and construction sector*. Global Alliance for Buildings and Construction. www.globalabc.org.
- 64) Well Cornell Medicine Library. (2025). Systematic reviews: Scoping reviews. <https://med.cornell.libguides.com/systematicreviews/scopingreviews>
- 65) World Bank. (2018). *Policy matters: Regulatory indicators for sustainable energy (RISE)*. World Bank Group.
- 66) Yang, Z., Yuan, X., Hu, J., Liu, D., & Tang, W. (2024). The impact of the proportion of renewable energy consumption on geopolitical risks in the United States and the United Kingdom. *Energy Exploration and Exploitation*, 42(6), 1958–1986. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01445987241250268>
- 67) Zhong, L., Yuan, J., Zhao, X., Segun, G. A., & Vakili, M. (2021). Indoor environmental health assessment in eco-building and its case study. *Atmosphere*, 12(794), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos12060794>